

EFFECTS OF DEBONDS ON THE STRENGTH OF COMPOSITE PLATES

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The effect of debonds on composite structures under compressive loads is investigated in this paper. Because of the inclusion of debonds, unsymmetric laminated rectangular plates are considered. The resulting bending-extension coupling is included and is shown to be quite significant for thin laminates typical of debonded regions. The solution technique is based on the Theorem of Minimum Potential Energy; and both simply supported and clamped boundaries are considered. The need to include transverse shear deformation in the analysis is documented. Also, the range of applicability of the reduced stiffness matrix technique for such plates is stated.

The consideration of non-rectangular boundaries, as would normally occur for debonded regions, has been included through a finite element study. Using the results of this study, an effective laminated plate theory for irregularly shaped debonded regions is proposed.

Introduction

An understanding of the influence of interlaminar damage on the strength of composite material structures is necessary if these materials are to be used effectively. In the manufacture of laminated structures it is almost impossible not to form debonded regions. And, in service, composite materials can form areas of debond between laminae. These faults result from manufacturing error and accidents. Therefore, the importance of such irregularities on the strength of the structure must be determined to ascertain the need for repair.

This work studies the effects of debonds on composite structures under compressive loads. Fabrication techniques for composite material plates demand certain plate symmetry to avoid warpage during the cure process. The inclusion of a debond, however, allows unsymmetric laminates to be formed. In order to consider such structures, a laminated plate theory for rectangular plates which includes unsymmetric effects is presented. Previous studies have been limited to symmetric, balanced, or special laminates where bending-stretching coupling can be neglected (1-9). The size of the debond region and the resulting laminates formed may cause transverse shear deformation effects to be excessive. Therefore, this factor will be studied as well.

Laminated Plate Theory

Formulation of Theory

The boundary conditions associated with the delaminated portion of the plate are, at best, questionable. To handle such arbitrary boundary conditions, a variational solution technique can be employed.

To formulate an expression for the potential energy of a laminated plate of composite material needed in such an analysis, consider a laminate of n laminae, each with the principal material axes (1-2 axes) making an angle θ with the plate geometry coordinates (x - y axes). Making the usual assumptions for such plates (3,8), but including the effect of transverse shear deformation, gives the following stress-strain relations for each lamina:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \sigma_{xy} \\ \sigma_{yz} \\ \sigma_{xz} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{12} & Q_{16} & 0 & 0 \\ Q_{12} & Q_{22} & Q_{26} & 0 & 0 \\ Q_{16} & Q_{26} & Q_{66} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & Q_{44} & Q_{45} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & Q_{45} & Q_{55} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_y \\ \epsilon_{xy} \\ \epsilon_{yz} \\ \epsilon_{xz} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where σ is the stress tensor, ϵ is the strain tensor, and the Q_{ij} are given in (3,8).

The displacements for the plate can be taken to be of the form:

$$\begin{aligned}
 u(x,y,z) &= u^{\circ}(x,y) + zF_1(x,y) \\
 v(x,y,z) &= v^{\circ}(x,y) + zF_2(x,y) \\
 w(x,y,z) &= w(x,y)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{2}$$

where u , v , and w are the displacements in the x , y , and z directions, respectively. u° and v° are mid-surface displacements while F_1 and F_2 allow for the inclusion of transverse shear deformation in the theory (10).² Integration with respect to z of the stress-strain relations gives expressions for the stress resultants and couples:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N \\ Q \\ M \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A & 0 & B \\ 0 & \bar{A} & 0 \\ B & 0 & D \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon \\ \bar{\epsilon} \\ \kappa \end{Bmatrix}
 \tag{3}$$

where the A , B , and D matrices represent the extensional, coupling, and bending stiffnesses of the laminated plate. N , Q , and M are the stress resultants and couples:

$$N = \begin{Bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}; \quad Q = \begin{Bmatrix} Q_y \\ Q_x \end{Bmatrix}; \quad M = \begin{Bmatrix} M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}
 \tag{4}$$

ϵ and $\bar{\epsilon}$ are the mid-surface strain components

$$\epsilon = \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_x^{\circ} \\ \epsilon_y^{\circ} \\ \epsilon_{xy}^{\circ} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{\partial u^{\circ}}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial v^{\circ}}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial u^{\circ}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v^{\circ}}{\partial x} \end{Bmatrix}
 \tag{5}$$

$$\bar{\epsilon} = \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_{yz}^{\circ} \\ \epsilon_{xz}^{\circ} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} F_2 + \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \\ F_1 + \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \end{Bmatrix}$$

and κ are the plate curvatures (3):

$$\kappa = \begin{Bmatrix} \kappa_x \\ \kappa_y \\ \kappa_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{\partial F_1}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial F_2}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial F_1}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial F_2}{\partial x} \end{Bmatrix}
 \tag{6}$$

\bar{A} relates the Q and $\bar{\epsilon}$ matrices (11):

$$\bar{A} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{44} & A_{45} \\ A_{45} & A_{55} \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

Substitution into the Theorem of Minimum Potential Energy for a rectangular laminated plate gives the following expression for the potential energy V (11):

$$\begin{aligned} V = & \frac{1}{2} \iint \{ N_x \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)^2 + N_y \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right)^2 + 2N_{xy} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right) \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right) \} \cdot dx \, dy \\ & + \frac{1}{2} \iint \{ A_{11} \left(\frac{\partial u^0}{\partial x} \right)^2 + 2A_{12} \left(\frac{\partial u^0}{\partial x} \right) \left(\frac{\partial v^0}{\partial y} \right) + 2A_{16} \left[\left(\frac{\partial u^0}{\partial x} \right) \cdot \right. \\ & \cdot \left. \left(\frac{\partial u^0}{\partial y} \right) + \left(\frac{\partial u^0}{\partial x} \right) \left(\frac{\partial v^0}{\partial x} \right) \right] + A_{22} \left(\frac{\partial v^0}{\partial y} \right)^2 + 2A_{26} \left[\left(\frac{\partial u^0}{\partial y} \right) \left(\frac{\partial v^0}{\partial y} \right) \right. \\ & + \left. \left(\frac{\partial v^0}{\partial x} \right) \left(\frac{\partial v^0}{\partial y} \right) \right] + A_{66} \left[\left(\frac{\partial u^0}{\partial y} \right)^2 + 2 \left(\frac{\partial u^0}{\partial y} \right) \left(\frac{\partial v^0}{\partial x} \right) + \left(\frac{\partial v^0}{\partial x} \right)^2 \right] \\ & + A_{44} \left[\left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right)^2 + 2F_2 \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right) + F_2^2 \right] + 2A_{45} \left[\left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right) \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right) + \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right) F_2 \right. \\ & + \left. F_1 \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right) + F_1 F_2 \right] + A_{55} \left[\left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)^2 + 2F_1 \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right) + F_1^2 \right] \\ & + 2B_{11} \left(\frac{\partial u^0}{\partial x} \right) \left(\frac{\partial F_1}{\partial x} \right) + 2B_{12} \left[\left(\frac{\partial u^0}{\partial x} \right) \left(\frac{\partial F_2}{\partial y} \right) + \left(\frac{\partial v^0}{\partial y} \right) \left(\frac{\partial F_1}{\partial x} \right) \right] \\ & + 2B_{16} \left[\left(\frac{\partial F_1}{\partial x} \right) \left(\frac{\partial u^0}{\partial y} \right) + \left(\frac{\partial F_1}{\partial x} \right) \left(\frac{\partial v^0}{\partial x} \right) + \left(\frac{\partial u^0}{\partial x} \right) \left(\frac{\partial F_1}{\partial y} \right) + \left(\frac{\partial u^0}{\partial x} \right) \cdot \right. \\ & \cdot \left. \left(\frac{\partial F_2}{\partial x} \right) \right] + 2B_{22} \left(\frac{\partial v^0}{\partial y} \right) \left(\frac{\partial F_2}{\partial y} \right) + 2B_{26} \left[\left(\frac{\partial u^0}{\partial y} \right) \left(\frac{\partial F_2}{\partial y} \right) \right. \\ & + \left. \left(\frac{\partial v^0}{\partial x} \right) \left(\frac{\partial F_2}{\partial y} \right) + \left(\frac{\partial F_1}{\partial y} \right) \left(\frac{\partial v^0}{\partial y} \right) + \left(\frac{\partial F_2}{\partial x} \right) \left(\frac{\partial v^0}{\partial y} \right) \right] \\ & + 2B_{66} \left[\left(\frac{\partial u^0}{\partial y} \right) \left(\frac{\partial F_1}{\partial y} \right) + \left(\frac{\partial u^0}{\partial y} \right) \left(\frac{\partial F_2}{\partial x} \right) + \left(\frac{\partial v^0}{\partial x} \right) \left(\frac{\partial F_1}{\partial y} \right) \right. \\ & + \left. \left(\frac{\partial v^0}{\partial x} \right) \left(\frac{\partial F_2}{\partial x} \right) \right] + D_{11} \left(\frac{\partial F_1}{\partial x} \right)^2 + 2D_{12} \left(\frac{\partial F_2}{\partial y} \right) \left(\frac{\partial F_1}{\partial x} \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + 2D_{16} \left[\left(\frac{\partial F_1}{\partial x} \right) \left(\frac{\partial F_1}{\partial y} \right) + \left(\frac{\partial F_1}{\partial x} \right) \left(\frac{\partial F_2}{\partial x} \right) \right] + D_{22} \left(\frac{\partial F_2}{\partial y} \right)^2 \\
& + 2D_{26} \left[\left(\frac{\partial F_1}{\partial y} \right) \left(\frac{\partial F_2}{\partial y} \right) + \left(\frac{\partial F_2}{\partial x} \right) \left(\frac{\partial F_2}{\partial y} \right) \right] + D_{66} \left[\left(\frac{\partial F_1}{\partial y} \right)^2 \right. \\
& \left. + 2 \left(\frac{\partial F_1}{\partial y} \right) \left(\frac{\partial F_2}{\partial x} \right) + \left(\frac{\partial F_2}{\partial x} \right)^2 \right] \} dx dy \tag{8}
\end{aligned}$$

Method of Analysis

The variables in V are u^0 , v^0 , w , F_1 , and F_2 . To find the buckling load, we will assume forms for u^0 , v^0 , and w . To obtain approximate expressions for F_1 and F_2 as functions of these, the procedure is to obtain Euler-Lagrange equations for the plate, reduce them to those for a beam in the x -direction, and solve for F_1 as a function of u^0 and w (11). This yields

$$F_1(x, y) = - \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} - \left[\left(\frac{D_{11} A_{11} - B_{11}^2}{A_{11}} \right) \left(\frac{A_{55} + N_x}{A_{55}} \right) \right] \frac{\partial^3 w}{\partial x^3} \tag{9a}$$

Similarly, F_2 is approximated by

$$F_2(x, y) = - \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} - \left[\left(\frac{D_{22} A_{22} - B_{22}^2}{A_{22}} \right) \left(\frac{A_{44} + N_y}{A_{44}} \right) \right] \frac{\partial^3 w}{\partial y^3} \tag{9b}$$

The classical plate theory is obtained by letting

$$F_1 = - \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \quad ; \quad F_2 = - \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \tag{10}$$

The forms of u^0 , v^0 , and w assumed in this study are

$$u^0(x, y) = \sum_i \sum_j U_{ij} \sin \frac{i\pi x}{a} \cos \frac{j\pi y}{b} \tag{11a}$$

$$v^0(x, y) = \sum_i \sum_j V_{ij} \cos \frac{i\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{j\pi y}{b}$$

and, for simply supported edges:

$$w^0(x, y) = \sum_i \sum_j W_{ij} \sin \frac{i\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{j\pi y}{b} \tag{11b}$$

whereas for clamped edges:

$$w^0(x,y) = \sum_i \sum_j W_{ij} \left[\cos \frac{(i-1)\pi x}{a} - \cos \frac{(i+1)\pi x}{a} \right] \left[\cos \frac{(j-1)\pi y}{b} - \cos \frac{(j+1)\pi y}{b} \right] \quad (11c)$$

The summations were taken from one to five.

Results and Conclusions

Laminated Plate Theory

Three theories are considered in the application of this analysis to symmetric and unsymmetric laminates

- (a) Theory I: Uncoupled theory in which only the transverse deflection is included and transverse shear deformation is neglected. This is equivalent to most presently available analyses.
- (b) Theory II: Laminated plate theory including the coupling of in-plane and transverse displacements but neglecting transverse shear deformation. For symmetric laminates, this reduces to Theory I.
- (c) Theory III: Laminated plate theory including both transverse shear deformation and the coupling of in-plane and transverse displacements.

To illustrate the theories and to show their regions of applicability, several examples are presented. Although the main interest is non-symmetric laminates produced by debonds, results for a symmetric laminate are also presented for comparison purposes. The parameters of interest are plate size and shape and plate boundary conditions.

For the laminate, a $[0/\pm 45/0/\mp 45]_S$ layup was chosen for the symmetric case while a $[0/\pm 45/0/\mp 45]$ layup was picked for the unsymmetric example. Previous studies have shown that laminates with very few laminae can give substantially different results than those with more than six or eight plies; the examples minimize this effect and give results typical of other configurations.

Both simply supported and clamped boundary conditions are investigated. Plate geometry was varied by considering different aspect ratios, a/b , and different thickness to width ratios, h/a . A high-modulus graphite, with a Young's modulus ratio of E_1/E_2 of 40 and a Young's modulus to shear modulus ratio of E_1/G_{12} of greater than 20 which is typical of composite materials, is used in the examples.

The results of the parametric studies are shown in Figures 1-4. As was stated earlier, Theories I and II coincide for symmetric laminates. The different boundary conditions produce changes similar to those published for plates of isotropic and orthotropic materials (3,8).

The data show the need to include transverse shear deformation even for plates with thickness to width ratios of 0.02. Such ratios can occur quite easily in debonded regions. Figures 3 and 4 also demonstrate the need to include the non-symmetry effects in the analysis of asymmetric plates.

One of the major results of the parametric studies is the comparison of the different theories. By neglecting coupling and transverse shear deformation effects, the critical buckling load is overestimated. This overestimation

FIGURE 1. BUCKLING LOAD N_x FOR SIMPLY SUPPORTED SYMMETRIC LAMINATE OF HIGH MODULUS GRAPHITE

FIGURE 2. BUCKLING LOAD N_x FOR CLAMPED SYMMETRIC LAMINATE OF HIGH MODULUS GRAPHITE

FIGURE 3. BUCKLING LOAD N_x FOR SIMPLY SUPPORTED ASYMMETRIC LAMINATE OF HIGH MODULUS GRAPHITE

FIGURE 4. BUCKLING LOAD N_x FOR CLAMPED ASYMMETRIC LAMINATE OF HIGH MODULUS GRAPHITE

is significant for asymmetric laminated plates for all geometries and can, in some cases, produce order of magnitude errors.

Therefore, when considering debonded laminated plates, the stability analysis must include the asymmetry of the composite, allow for transverse shear deformation, and incorporate the coupling of in-plane and transverse displacements. All of these effects can significantly alter the theoretical critical buckling load.

Reduced Stiffness Matrix Theory

The reduced bending stiffness approximation, first introduced by Reissner and Stavsky and expanded upon by Ashton and Whitney, forms an analysis technique for unsymmetric plates which uncouples the bending and stretching problems (3). This method can greatly reduce the energy expended in obtaining a solution for an unsymmetric laminate. Ashton and Whitney showed this procedure to yield acceptable results for simply supported plates when investigating plate deflections under static loadings. The possibility of extending this technique to the stability of plates with simply supported and clamped boundaries has not been considered by earlier researchers. Therefore, the comparison of the reduced stiffness approximation and the general theory is appropriate.

Using this theory for the simply supported asymmetric laminates considered in Figure 3, a 5 to 10% overestimation is obtained for the buckling load when $0.01 \leq h/a \leq 0.02$. This error increases to over 20% for $h/a \geq 0.03$. Errors of similar magnitudes are obtained for the clamped laminates studied in Figure 4. As suspected, the reduced stiffness matrix theory gives good results for the buckling load for symmetric laminates with $h/a \leq 0.05$. This applies to both simply supported and clamped edges.

Consideration of Non-Rectangular Geometries

Although the analytical theory presented provides a basis upon which design calculations could be made, nonrectangular irregularities have not been included. To be able to obtain the necessary correction factors that are needed with such geometries, this problem has been studied through the use of the finite element method.

The complexity of the unbonded region in the composite plate requires that a three-dimensional isoparametric element with orthotropic material properties be used in the finite element analysis. To include the bending-twisting and bending-stretching coupling effects associated with an asymmetric laminate, at least two layers of elements through the thickness of the plate are required. The equivalence between the two-layered plate and the composite plate is obtained by using effective laminate properties (11).

The arrangement of elements and the appropriate boundary conditions to approximate simple and clamped edges were investigated and a system which was shown to be accurate for isotropic plates was employed to approximate these conditions.

The formulation of the buckling problem for the debond region was based on the geometric stiffness matrix method. Although an eigenvalue approach is possible, the geometric matrix method allows the investigator to choose the buckling mode. In the case of delaminated plates, the buckling mode must be the (1,1) mode; all other modes cause the buckled region to deform into the adjacent unbuckled region of the plate.

The geometric stiffness matrix technique is based on the realization that loading a plate in compression has the effect of reducing the bending stiffness. As the in-plane loading reaches the critical level, the bending stiffness approaches zero. The geometric stiffness matrix represents this dependence of in-plane stresses and strains on out of plane displacements; and is used to alter the stiffness matrix of the plate in such a manner as to produce a zero bending stiffness matrix when the in-plane load is the buckling load:

$$[K + \lambda K^d]\{u\} = 0$$

where:

- K = conventional stiffness matrix
- K^d = geometric stiffness matrix
- λ = eigenvalue associated with the buckling load
- u = displacement vector

Thus, the solution method includes the following steps:

- (a) determine the uncoupled small deflection theory stiffness matrix
- (b) calculate the displacements and internal stresses (σ_{ij}^0) due to the applied load
- (c) evaluate the geometric stiffness matrix for this internal stress level σ_{ij}^0 :

$$[K^d] = \int_V \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial N_1}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial N_1}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial N_1}{\partial z} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial N_8}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial N_8}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial N_8}{\partial z} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x^0 & \sigma_{xy}^0 & \sigma_{xz}^0 \\ \sigma_{xy}^0 & \sigma_y^0 & \sigma_{yz}^0 \\ \sigma_{xz}^0 & \sigma_{yz}^0 & \sigma_z^0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial N_1}{\partial x} & \dots & \frac{\partial N_8}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial N_1}{\partial y} & \dots & \frac{\partial N_8}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial N_1}{\partial z} & \dots & \frac{\partial N_8}{\partial z} \end{bmatrix} dV$$

where N_i are the interpolation functions for the isoparametric finite element.

- (d) recalculate the displacements based on a new total stiffness matrix equal to the sum of the geometric and small deflection theory stiffnesses.

Under a small applied lateral load, the displacements obtained in the first iteration represent the small deflection theory solution. The buckling load is found by observing the displacements of the second iteration. By

increasing the in-plane load, the displacements of the plate increase. At the same time as the in-plane load approaches its critical level, the bending stiffness of the plate approaches zero. When the in-plane load is above the critical level, the bending stiffness has theoretically become negative; this causes the lateral displacement to exhibit a change in sign. The buckling load is easily identified as the in-plane load where this takes place.

Using this approach, two plates - one symmetric and one asymmetric - were investigated under an in-plane load in the x-direction. The A, B, and D matrices for these plates were typical for composite materials. For each case, simple and clamped support conditions were investigated. A comparison of the finite element analysis and the analytical theory developed above was made in all cases.

Investigation of the results showed that the clamped support agreed more closely than the simply supported plates when comparing the two studies. Thus, the simple support case is the critical condition and only these results are given in Tables 1 and 2.

As shown in the Tables, the percent difference in the two theories decreased as the diameter of the circular plate increased. This is to be expected since, as the plate diameter increases, the effects of the boundary of the circular plate on the buckling load should have less effect on the behavior of the plate. And, thus, the circular and square plate boundary conditions should approximate each other. The data also show that, as the debond region approaches an elliptic form, the buckling load results for the two theories correspond more closely. This, again, is to be expected because of the similarity of the two boundary shapes. Finally, it is observed that the difference between the theories for the symmetric and asymmetric circular plates is approximately the same. Thus, laminate configuration has less of an effect on the buckling load than does the boundary geometry. However, this last conclusion is predicated on comparing the finite element result with a variational theory that includes the asymmetry effect.

In summary, debond geometry has a very definite effect on buckling load. As the size of the debond region decreases and as its shape becomes more circular, the buckling load may be as much as 50% less than that predicted using the variational theory for a rectangularly shaped plate.

Acknowledgments

This work was sponsored by the NASA-Langley Research Center under Grant No. 1304. This support is gratefully acknowledged.

Table 1. Symmetric Laminate with Simply Supported Edges

Geometry and Dimensions (for 0.028 in. thick plates)	Buckling Load, lb.		Percent Difference
	Finite Element Theory	Laminated Plate Theory	
Circular, 0.5 in. diameter, vs. 0.5 in. square plate	490	768	57
Circular, 1.0 in. diameter, vs. 1.0 in. square plate	255	384	50
Circular, 2.0 in. diameter, vs. 2.0 in. square plate	140	192	37
Square, 1.0 in. on sides	385	384	--
Elliptic, 1.0 x 0.5 in. axes	745	1030	38
Elliptic, 0.5 x 1.0 in. axes	435	519	19
Rectangular, 1.0 x 0.5 in.	900	1030	14

Table 2. Unsymmetric Laminate with Simply Supported Edges

Geometry and Dimensions (for 0.028 in. thick plates)	Buckling Load, lb.		Percent Difference
	Finite Element Theory	Laminated Plate Theory	
Circular, 0.5 in. diameter, vs. 0.5 in. square plate	220	349	59
Circular, 1.0 in. diameter, vs. 1.0 in. square plate	115	174	51
Circular, 2.0 in. diameter, vs. 2.0 in. square plate	65	87	34
Square, 1.0 in. on sides	150	174	16
Elliptic, 1.0 x 0.5 in. axes	275	334	21
Elliptic, 0.5 x 1.0 in. axes	300	334	11

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